

The second requirement shows how the design of a back-off strategy could prevent degraded service from crashing, which belongs to the second high-level goal of the Retry pattern. We formally specify the *NoCrash* property as an invariant: $NoCrash \triangleq Len(calls) < ServerCrashAt$, which reads in English as: *The number of requests sent to the service must never exceed the service capacity*. The model checker shows that the design specification **does not** satisfy the property *NoCrash*. The counterexample shows a trace where the number of requests in the variable *schedule* is 2 with zero delays (ready to be retried by client). In the next state, the variable *calls* has five requests, including three, which is the constant number of requests and two additional retried requests. Therefore, in total, the number of requests sent to the service is five. The edge case in the design of the Retry pattern is that: *Re-sending large enough amount of requests, which have the same back-off delay, cause crash of the service*.

4) *Results and Discussion*: According to the definition of sensitivity point and the found edge case, we derive the

Sensitivity point in the design of the Retry pattern as the *level of randomness in the back-off strategy*.

derive *level of randomness in the back-off strategy* as the sensitivity point in the design of the Retry pattern. However, in the design of the Retry pattern, there is no description of the randomness. Therefore, the

Risk in the design of the Retry pattern is that there is no decision on the level of randomness in the back-off strategy.

We investigated both *Resilience4j* and *Polly* implementation of Retry pattern. Developers *Resilience4j* can choose `ofExponentialRandomBackoff` interval function (among few more) as a back-off strategy. While in *Polly* there is an extensive discussion on different implementations of randomness. We have to state that, in reality implementing perfect randomness is hard. Therefore, application designers need to be aware of imperfect randomness and make suitable application-level decisions. For example, they can use a rate limiter pattern on the service side.

We decided to change our design specification and add randomness to our back-off strategy concerning the Retry pattern. We modified the design specification and specified randomness so that no two requests have the same delay value (check the online appendix). Now the design of the Retry pattern satisfies the *NoCrash* property.